

those in Peta, IR8, and IR32, but the sclerenchymatous cell tissue bordering the central vascular bundle and the abscission layer is much narrower.

Since Sukhwel 20 tends to shed its spikelets with relative ease, it may be

reasonable to conclude that varieties with relatively larger parenchymatous cells in the abscission layer and a thinner sclerenchymatous tissue (fewer cell layers) bordering the abscission layer and

the central vascular bundle of the pedicel are essentially more fragile (i.e. mechanically weaker). Consequently their spikelets are more susceptible to shattering. ■

Performance of some long-duration semidwarf rice cultures in relation to their suitability for medium lowland cultivation during the wet season

P. Mukherjee, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India

An investigation to identify promising cultures for medium lowland cultivation (20 to 40 cm water level) used materials selected from coordinated trials at Chinsurah, Cuttack, and IRRI, Philippines.

Twelve long-duration entries suitable for medium lowland cultivation were tested in 1976 and 1977 (see table).

Yield of long-duration semidwarf rice cultures on medium lowlands during 1976-77 wet season, India.

Culture	Yield (t/ha)	
	1976	1977
Pankaj (check)	5.7	4.5
IET2911	4.6	3.2
IET3257	4.6	2.9
IR32	4.5	3.4
HTA448	4.5	2.8
IET4087	4.4	3.1
IET3235	4.2	3.3
HTA108	3.8	3.5
IR34	3.8	3.0
Pankaj (M) 91	3.1	4.2
CNBP153-58-2	3.5	3.0
CNBP-134-134-1	3.4	2.3
LSD (.05)	0.4	0.6

The experimental design was randomized complete block with four replications. Plots were 4.8 x 2.6 m with plant spacing of 20 x 15 cm and fertilizer applications of 80 kg N/ha, 40 kg P/ha, and 40 kg K/ha.

Pankaj was statistically superior to all the other varieties in 1976. Yields from IET2911, IET3257, IR32, HTA448, IET4087, and IET3235 were statistically the same. Pankaj, though the highest yielder in 1977, was statistically equal to Pankaj (M) 91. Yields from all the other cultures were statistically the same. The yield deviation between the 2 years may have been caused by environment. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Gall midge- and bacterial blight-resistant varieties for Madhya Pradesh, India

P. S. Shrivastava, B. O. Choudhary, R. K. Sahu, and V. N. Sahu, Central Rice Research Station, Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, India

Gall midge and bacterial blight are the two most frequent biological stresses on the paddy crop of eastern Madhya Pradesh. The average farmer cannot

afford plant protection measures against the two stresses. A breeding program for resistance to them was initiated at Raipur. Four improved varieties of different maturity groups, resistant to gall midge and bacterial blight and resistant to moderately resistant to several other pests, were developed. The varieties have performed well in farmers' fields and abundant seed is now available. Details of the varieties are:

Variety	Cross	Yield (t/ha)	Grain quality ^a	Days to maturity	Pest reaction ^b
R2384	R68-1/Jaya	3.4	MS	125	GM(R), SB(MR), LF(MR), BPH (MR), BLB(R)
R35-2752	IR22/W1263	3.7	LS	128	GM(R), SB(R), GLH(MR), BPH (MR), LF(MR), BB(R)
R35-2750	IR22/W1263	4.6	LB	132	GM(R), BB(R), HEL(R), RTV (R)
R35-2751	IR22/W1263	4.2	LB	135	CMCR), BB(R)
RP9-4	(check)	3.3	LB	135	GM(R)
RPW6-17	(check)	4.3	LB	140	GM(R)

^aMS = medium slender, LS = long slender, LB = long bold. ^bGM = gall midge, SB = shoot borer, LF = leaf folder, BPH = brown planthopper, GLH = green leafhopper, BB = bacterial blight, HEL = Helminthosporium brown spot, RTV = rice tungro virus, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

Sources of resistance to rice ragged stunt disease

A. Ghosh and V. T. John, All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Rice ragged stunt, a virus disease transmitted by the brown planthopper, was first observed in the Philippines in 1978 and has since been reported in Thailand, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and in West Bengal, Orissa, and Tamil Nadu states in India. AICRIP screening programs were initiated to find sources of resistance to the disease. During 1979 kharif, 80 varieties were screened in the greenhouse. Most of the high-yielding semidwarfs were susceptible (50-80% infection). But despite artificial inoculation, certain varieties – Pokkali, Getu, PTB18, PTB33, T141, Hitam, Benong 1, Tamiang, Slammat, Benong 3, Boak, and Boegimba – produced no symptoms. ■